

Identification and classification of aortic dissection in 3D CT scans

Parminder Kaur^a, Ashar Asif^b, Raghu Lakshminarayan^b, Dorothy Monekosso^c, Paolo Remagnino^{a,*}

^aComputer Science Department, Durham University, UK

^bHull University Teaching Hospitals NHS Trust, UK

^cCollege of Engineering and Physical Sciences, Aston University, UK

Abstract

Aortic dissection (AD) is a time-critical condition associated with rapid disease progression, catastrophic complications and a high mortality rate. Classified into two subtypes by the Stanford Criteria, Type A and Type B (TAAD and TBAD), AD's management is tailored to the unique risks and complications each subtype carries, and therefore, its classification is as essential as its diagnosis. Its diagnosis relies on promptly performed contrast-enhanced CT of the aorta. So, we propose an automated segmentation and classification approach for AD identification, which can be applied on the obtained CT scans. Firstly, the CT scans are pre-processed to enhance the features (mainly the aortic region) for further processing. It is followed by a 3D UNet-based segmentation approach to identify the segments (masks) on the aorta. Afterwards, a patient-level classification is performed based on the identified segments in the scans. Our dataset, curated and annotated by clinicians, consists of three classes: TAAD, TBAD and Normal (NoAD). Classically, CT scan annotation is resource-intensive, so to avoid this, clinicians have performed a rough labelling of the aorta, comprising four classes. A less resource-intensive labelling method can mean ease of curating a larger and diverse dataset, resulting in generalisable models that are clinically applicable. The extensive experiments and results demonstrate the effectiveness of the proposed technique for AD recognition in terms of Dice score and scan-level classification accuracy (93.33%). Our AD detection and classification algorithm has the potential for rapid and accurate diagnosis and initiation of life-saving treatment, following soon after.

Keywords: AD classification, aortic dissection, nnUNetv2, 3D CT scans, image segmentation

1. Introduction

Aortic dissection (AD) is a rapidly evolving pathology and one of the leading causes of cardiovascular death. It occurs when the layers lining the walls of the aorta, the main distributor of blood in the body, peel apart from each other, forming a flap and eventually a dead-end where blood pools. AD can extend and progress, weakening the aorta, putting it at risk of rupture, or can involve the branches, causing the death of key organs such as the kidneys, bowel, brain and heart [1]. It is a low-frequency, high-risk pathology with an incidence rate between 0.61 and 7.2 per 100,000 [2], and half of these patients die before reaching the hospital [3]. Diagnosed by computer tomography (CT) imaging, AD appears in around 2.5% of CT scans performed in an emergency department [4]. A CT scan of the aorta produces images as slices of the aorta itself and other neighbouring organs [5]. Given the complexity of the aorta's shape, slices acquired through the chest capture both ascending and descending aspects of the aorta, while those acquired through the abdomen only capture the descending aorta. Some

views of the aorta show elliptical shapes. The CT scan is usually combined with angiography (CTA), using the injection of radio-opaque contrast to highlight the blood vessels and provide an ability to determine the integrity of the vessel wall [6]. Despite its significant sequelae, a diagnosis of AD is often missed [7]. Also, in a busy emergency department where hundreds of CT scans are performed per day, high cognitive load can result in significant findings being overlooked by the interpreter, or scans with AD are buried in work lists and are interpreted after a significant time period has lapsed.

Figure 1: A slice from a CT scan from each of the classes (TAAD, TBAD, NonAD) used in the dataset. The red arrows depict the aortic dissection in the case of TAAD and TBAD, and the green arrow represents the normal aorta.

*Corresponding author

Email addresses: parminder.kaur@durham.ac.uk, parminder1050@gmail.com (Parminder Kaur), ashar.asif1@nhs.net (Ashar Asif), raghu.l@nhs.net (Raghu Lakshminarayan), d.monekosso@aston.ac.uk (Dorothy Monekosso), paolo.remagnino@durham.ac.uk (Paolo Remagnino)

classes along with the normal CT scan on a single slice of a scan. Patients with TAAD (involving the ascending aorta) require immediate surgery, which is an open chest aortic surgery and is confined to highly specialised major centres. On the other hand, TBAD (involving the descending aorta) can be clinically stable and can be managed with a "watch-and-wait" approach, routine monitoring with annual scanning. A technology that can alert the emergency department team of the presence of AD in a scan immediately after the scan is performed, even before formal reporting, could potentially save lives. It would prioritise the scan for a formal report and information dissemination to local and tertiary care teams so that the patient can be appropriately triaged for immediate surgery.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) has shown potential within cardiovascular imaging, particularly automated measurements [8], segmentation [9] and disease detection [10], in both dedicated and non-dedicated imaging. Similarly, there is promise with the application of computer vision algorithms to detect AD from CT imaging; our meta-analysis of published performance data of AD detection algorithms yielded a pooled sensitivity of 94%, specificity of 88% and AUC (Area Under Curve) of 96.7%. However, these models were trained on limited-sized datasets from single centres and were based on a narrow spectrum of the disease. Whilst demonstrating good performance, the applicability of AI in this context is still in its infancy. Most of the existing AI algorithms in this field only detect AD and do not classify it, which is required for further action. Moreover, they are supervised algorithms (common within radiology [11]) and require data annotation, which is performed manually. A major barrier to curating the dataset lies in the pixel-level annotation procedure, which is exhaustive and time-consuming.

So, in this paper, we propose an easy and rough annotation procedure that is less time-consuming and assess its feasibility in detecting and classifying AD from CT imaging. We used the data annotated using this technique to train the state-of-the-art nnUNet v2 segmentation model [12], [13] for segmenting the different sections of aorta as per the labels. After obtaining the masks, patient-level classification is performed based on the presence of particular labels and their Dice scores.

The significant contributions are as follows:

1. We propose a simple labelling procedure, which is less resource and time-intensive than the existing methods and obtains considerable accuracy for AD classification.
2. We leverage the nnUNet v2 model to perform automatic segmentation of the aorta (four labels) in CT scans.
3. A simple yet effective procedure has been used for patient-level classification based on the segmentation model's results (presence of segments and Dice score threshold).

2. Methodology

2.1. Labelling procedure

The data annotation is performed roughly (not precisely as per the aorta's exact shape) on a pixel level around the aorta slice-by-slice. An irregular polygon is drawn around the

aorta, ensuring it covers the whole aorta. The annotation consists of four labels: *dissected_pre*, *dissected_post*, *non_pre*, and *non_post* where "pre" and "post" refers to the location of the dissection relative to the subclavian artery, a branch of the aorta acting as a boundary between TAAD and TBAD, respectively. A scan containing the label *dissected_pre* is classified as TAAD; if it contains *dissected_post* without *dissected_pre* it is classified as TBAD, and if it contains *non_pre* and *non_post* labels only, then the scan is classified as non-AD.

2.2. AD segmentation and classification

Let $D = (S_i, M_i, C_i)_{i=1}^N$ represent the total CT scan dataset, where each $S_i = (d, h, w)$ represents a CT scan, $M_i = (d, h, w)$ is the corresponding mask and also $M_i \subset \{\text{background}, \text{dissected_pre}, \text{dissected_post}, \text{non_pre}, \text{non_post}\}$, comprises five labels including "background", and $C_i \in \{TAAD, TBAD, NonAD\}$ is the class of the scan. The value of h (height) and w (width) is 512, however, d (depth) is different for each scan. The total number (N) of scans is divided into training and validation set (N_{tr}) and testing set (N_{ts}), creating the train data $D_{train} = (S_j, M_j, C_j)_{j=1}^{N_{tr}}$ and test data $D_{test} = (S_j, M_j, C_j)_{j=1}^{N_{ts}}$. The input provided to the nnUNet model for training is in the format $(S_k, M_k)_{k=1}^{N_{tr}}$ and in the output, we obtain the predicted masks $(M_k)_{k=1}^{N_{ts}}$ of shape (d, h, w) , along with the Dice scores for each label in the mask. These Dice scores are used to predict the final class $(C_k)_{k=1}^{N_{ts}}$ corresponding to each scan (patient-level classification).

The proposed methodology is shown in Figure 2 by taking a single CT scan example. Initially, we have a set of CT scans and corresponding masks (comprising five classes, including background). They are provided as input to the nnUNet model to train it for segmenting the five labels. nnUNet creates five data splits (folds) during the data preparation phase, we can choose any one of the folds (by specifying the fold number 0, 1, 2, 3, 4 in the training command) for validation, and the rest of the data are used for training. All the folds can also be used for training without any validation data (where the fold is set as 'all' while training). In this study, three nnUNet v2 models are trained and tested using different configurations: a low-resolution model (*3d_lowres* with *fold=0*), a full-resolution model (*3d_fullres* with *fold=0*) and a full-resolution model trained on the entire dataset without separate validation data or validation is also performed on training data (*3d_fullres* with *fold='all'*). We will refer to this model as *3d_fullres_fall* to differentiate it from *3d_fullres*. More information about the model and the configurations can be found in [12], [13].

The loss function is calculated as the sum of cross-entropy and Dice loss. For each output, a corresponding ground truth segmentation mask is used for loss computation. For a test scan, nnUNet provides the mask (same size as the scan). Afterwards, patient-level classification is performed based on the presence of a particular label in the mask and the obtained Dice score of each label. The threshold value is set as 0.2 as per the lowest mean Dice score of any class. As the number of pixels of type A and B AD are quite low compared to normal cases (NonAD), their Dice score value is also low, especially type A. This is

Figure 2: The flow diagram of AD segmentation and classification. Here $dice_1$ and $dice_2$ depict the Dice scores of *dissected_pre* and *dissected_post* classes in a scan, respectively.

because the dissection happens in a small region of the scan, and the rest of the scan is normal similar to NonAD scan, which increases the normal region in the whole dataset. Our classifier is based on a simple threshold-based strategy on Dice scores. If the Dice score of class *dissected_pre* is greater than or equal to the threshold, then the scan is classified as "TAAD". If the Dice score of class *dissected_post* is greater than or equal to the threshold and the score of class *dissected_pre* is less than the threshold or it is NaN (which means not predicted by the model), then the scan is classified as "TBAD", otherwise it is classified as "NonAD".

3. Experimental analysis

3.1. Dataset

The dataset used for experimentation was collected by retrospectively searching the picture archiving and communication system (PACS) database based at a single regional tertiary vascular and cardiothoracic unit, following national and local ethics approval. Contrast-enhanced CTA scans performed between 2010 and 2023 were included and reviewed by two radiologists. The scans used for model development comprised the whole aorta, from the aortic root to the aortic bifurcation. CTA of solely the thorax or abdomen were excluded. The non-AD cohort includes scans demonstrating no aortopathy, as well as other abnormalities of the aorta, such as aneurysms, calcification, and thrombus. A selection of 103 scans were roughly annotated (36 TAAD, 35 TBAD and 32 nonAD). Training and validation are performed on 88 scans, and 15 scans (5 from each class) are used for testing. The results presented in the paper

are obtained from the test data. The scans and masks were converted to the *.nii.gz* format for providing input to the nnUNet model. Each scan had a slice size of 512x512 and a different number of slices, with a minimum of 500.

3.2. Implementation details

The experimentation was performed on NVIDIA TITAN RTX and NVIDIA RTX A6000 GPUs. All three configurations of nnUNet model are trained on our dataset for 100 epochs. We used the best checkpoints (*checkpoint_best.pth*) for the test data predictions. The default nnUNet parameters are used for pre-processing, training, and prediction, except for the number of processes, which were reduced to run the model on our GPUs effectively.

3.3. Results and discussion

Figures 3, 4, and 5 show the loss (training and validation) and Dice score plots of *3d_lowres*, *3d_fullres*, and *3d_fullres_fall* (*fold='all'*) configurations, respectively, while training. The blue line represents the training loss (*loss_tr*) and the red line represents the validation loss (*loss_val*). All models show a downward trend in loss over epochs, indicating learning. The green dashed line represents the pseudo Dice score, measuring segmentation accuracy. The solid green line represents its moving average, smoothing fluctuations. The training and validation loss in *3d_lowres* (Figure 3) decrease steadily over epochs, which shows that the model learned consistently but may have begun to overfit slightly toward the end. The pseudo-Dice score reaches a high value (around 0.82) by the end of training, with the moving average showing a stable plateau in the last 30

Figure 3: Training and validation loss and pseudo Dice scores of 3d_lowres configuration. The pseudo Dice curve represents the mean Dice coefficient across all target classes, with a smoothed version (moving average).

Figure 4: Training and validation loss and pseudo Dice scores of 3d_fullres configuration. The pseudo Dice curve represents the mean Dice coefficient across all target classes, with a smoothed version (moving average).

Figure 5: Training and validation loss and pseudo Dice scores of 3d_fullres_fall (fold='all') configuration. The pseudo Dice curve represents the mean Dice coefficient across all target classes, with a smoothed version (moving average).

epochs. The training loss drops steadily in 3d_fullres (Figure 4), and the validation loss follows a similar pattern, with no sharp divergence, showing a balanced learning process. The pseudo-Dice score gradually increases and stabilises around 0.78, slightly lower than Model A. The learning curves are smoother, indicating moderate learning dynamics. The training and validation losses in 3d_fullres_fall (Figure 5) follow a more fluctuating pattern compared to the other two models. The pseudo-Dice score increases more slowly. The moving average shows a flatter curve, reflecting slower and possibly less precise segmentation learning.

Table 1: Classwise mean Dice scores using all three configurations on test data

Labels	3d_lowres	3d_fullres	3d_fullres_fall
dissected_pre	0.2478	0.2071	0.1924
dissected_post	0.6312	0.4782	0.4555
non_pre	0.6887	0.6806	0.7016
non_post	0.6308	0.6174	0.5936
foreground mean	0.5496	0.4958	0.4858

Table 1 presents the mean Dice scores of each annotation class on test CT scans for all three configurations. The foreground mean is the mean of all four classes except the background. From the Dice score values, it can be observed that 3d_lowres has the highest Dice scores, then 3d_fullres, and 3d_fullres_all has the lowest. Tables 2 and 3, and 4 show the patient-level Dice scores of each class, groundtruth and predicted outcomes on test CT scans using 3d_lowres, 3d_fullres, and 3d_fullres_fall configurations, respectively. We are obtaining a patient-level classification accuracy of 80% (three incorrect predictions), 86.66% (two incorrect predictions), and 93.33% (only one incorrect prediction) using 3d_lowres, 3d_fullres, and 3d_fullres_fall correspondingly. Interestingly, while the 3d_lowres model achieved the highest segmentation Dice scores, it resulted in the poorest classification performance. Conversely, the 3d_fullres_fall trained on all data exhibited lower segmentation performance but yielded the best classification results. This behaviour could be explained by the following:

1. High Dice scores indicate accurate voxel-level matching, but this does not necessarily translate to improved scan-level classification. For instance, a model may predict structures more precisely (high Dice score), yet under-segment rare classes/labels critical for classification. However, models trained on all data (fold=all) may generalize better across all patient-level patterns even if voxel-level performance dips.
2. The model trained on all data is optimized on the entire training set, without validation monitoring. As a result, it may slightly overfit or diverge in Dice, but learn more diverse representations, improving downstream classification that aggregates over segment presence or quality.
3. The low-resolution model may focus more on shape and coarse boundaries, inflating Dice scores for large regions but losing finer structure, which could affect classification relying on class-specific thresholds. In contrast, full-resolution models may better capture small but discriminative structures essential for diagnosis.
4. Classification based on segment thresholds can be affected by false negatives in small structures. A model with high mean Dice might still miss rare class segments entirely, leading to classification failure, whereas a lower-Dice model might catch enough of the rare classes to trigger the correct scan-level label.

Table 2: Patient-level Dice scores, groundtruth and predicted outcomes on test CT scans using *3d.Lowres* configuration

CT	dissected_pre	dissected_post	non_pre	non_post	Actual	Predicted
1	0	nan	0.6951	0.9066	TAAD	NonAD
2	0.0256	0.9081	0.7362	0.3851	TAAD	TBAD
3	0.8856	0.8877	0	0.5096	TAAD	TAAD
4	0.8902	0.7455	0.5435	0.0999	TAAD	TAAD
5	0.9242	0.8780	0	0	TAAD	TAAD
6	0	0.8226	0.8935	0.7366	TBAD	TBAD
7	nan	0.0000	0.8942	0.8485	TBAD	NonAD
8	0	0.9096	0.9068	0.4124	TBAD	TBAD
9	0	0.9078	0.9270	0.5819	TBAD	TBAD
10	0	0.8836	0.8734	0.8162	TBAD	TBAD
11	nan	nan	0.8106	0.8313	NonAD	NonAD
12	nan	0	0.8531	0.6786	NonAD	NonAD
13	0	0	0.4816	0.8955	NonAD	NonAD
14	0	nan	0.8146	0.9121	NonAD	NonAD
15	nan	nan	0.9001	0.8472	NonAD	NonAD

Table 3: Patient-level Dice scores, groundtruth and predicted outcomes on test CT scans using *3d.fullres* configuration

CT	dissected_pre	dissected_post	non_pre	non_post	Actual	Predicted
1	0	0	0.7382	0.9136	TAAD	NonAD
2	0	0.9004	0.7522	0.5570	TAAD	TBAD
3	0.8958	0.8594	0	0.7088	TAAD	TAAD
4	0.8982	0.8019	0.0490	0.1408	TAAD	TAAD
5	0.8990	0.8451	0	0	TAAD	TAAD
6	0	0.7421	0.8975	0.8647	TBAD	TBAD
7	nan	0.3731	0.9141	0.8490	TBAD	TBAD
8	0	0.8993	0.9037	0.1743	TBAD	TBAD
9	0	0.8883	0.9242	0.4238	TBAD	TBAD
10	0	0.8633	0.8648	0.7598	TBAD	TBAD
11	nan	0	0.7758	0.7842	NonAD	NonAD
12	0	0	0.8292	0.6946	NonAD	NonAD
13	0	0	0.7545	0.7951	NonAD	NonAD
14	0	0	0.9024	0.8352	NonAD	NonAD
15	0	0	0.9035	0.7597	NonAD	NonAD

The above findings highlight a key distinction between segmentation quality and clinical classification utility, suggesting that model selection for downstream tasks should not rely solely on Dice metrics but also consider task-specific outcomes such as diagnostic sensitivity.

4. Conclusion

The proposed work introduced a simple yet effective annotation procedure for AD recognition and classification. The nnUNet v2 segmentation model has been utilised for predicting four different labels on the aorta as per the annotations. After retrieving the masks from the segmentation model, the patient-

Table 4: Patient-level Dice scores, groundtruth and predicted outcomes on test CT scans using *3d_fullres_fall* configuration

CT	dissected_pre	dissected_post	non_pre	non_post	Actual	Predicted
1	0.2834	0	0.7394	0.8853	TAAD	TAAD
2	0.0011	0.8595	0.7617	0.4442	TAAD	TBAD
3	0.8862	0.8264	0	0.662	TAAD	TAAD
4	0.9069	0.7709	0.4959	0.1105	TAAD	TAAD
5	0.8082	0.7906	0	0	TAAD	TAAD
6	0	0.7061	0.8894	0.8589	TBAD	TBAD
7	0	0.2902	0.9058	0.8301	TBAD	TBAD
8	0	0.8645	0.9129	0.1506	TBAD	TBAD
9	0	0.8698	0.9203	0.2134	TBAD	TBAD
10	0	0.8545	0.8679	0.7194	TBAD	TBAD
11	0	0	0.7855	0.799	NonAD	NonAD
12	0	0	0.8322	0.7403	NonAD	NonAD
13	0	0	0.5976	0.8144	NonAD	NonAD
14	0	0	0.9086	0.8742	NonAD	NonAD
15	0	0	0.9074	0.8017	NonAD	NonAD

level classification is performed based on the Dice score threshold for each of the labels present in the masks. After the experimentation, this annotation procedure is found to be useful for patient-level classification as we obtain 93.33% accuracy (only one wrong prediction) on test (unseen) data using 4 model configuration. In future, this approach can be extended further by incorporating a pre-processing step to enhance the features of the aorta, which may further increase the patient-level classification accuracy. Moreover, we are still in the process of collecting data and annotating it. So we will test the approach with a larger number of CT scans which may further improve the segmentation and classification performance.

Acknowledgements

This work was supported by the Impact Acceleration Accounts (IAA) fund by Durham University, UK.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to impact the work reported in this article.

Data availability

Data used in this research would not be shared as they are confidential patient data collected from NHS Trust.

References

- [1] T. Fukui, Management of acute aortic dissection and thoracic aortic rupture, *Journal of Intensive Care* 6 (2018) 1–8.
- [2] M. Czerny, M. Grabenwöger, T. Berger, V. Aboyans, A. Della Corte, E. P. Chen, N. D. Desai, J. Dumfarth, J. A. Elefteriades, C. D. Etz, K. M. Kim, M. Kreibich, M. Lescan, L. Di Marco, A. Martens, C. A. Mestres, M. Milojevic, C. A. Nienaber, G. Piffaretti, O. Preventza, E. Quintana, B. Rylski, C. L. Schlett, F. Schoenhoff, S. Trimarchi, K. Tsagakis, E. S. D. Group, Eacts/sts guidelines for diagnosing and treating acute and chronic syndromes of the aortic organ, *European Journal of Cardio-Thoracic Surgery* 65 (2) (2024) ezad426. arXiv:https://academic.oup.com/ejcts/article-pdf/65/2/ezad426/58464393/ezad426.pdf, doi:10.1093/ejcts/ezad426. URL <https://doi.org/10.1093/ejcts/ezad426>
- [3] K. Booth, et al., Acute aortic dissection (aad)—a lethal disease: the epidemiology, pathophysiology and natural history, *The British Journal of Cardiology* 30 (1) (2023) 9.
- [4] R. Ohle, O. Anjum, H. Bleeker, S. McIsaac, What is the specificity of the aortic dissection detection risk score in a low-prevalence population?, *Academic Emergency Medicine* 26 (6) (2019) 632–638.
- [5] J. Hsieh, T. Flohr, Computed tomography recent history and future perspectives, *Journal of Medical Imaging* 8 (5) (2021) 052109–052109.
- [6] R. Jamieson, A. Kharabish, M. Radiké, Vascular abnormalities not to miss on routine chest ct: A pictorial review, *European Journal of Radiology* (2024) 111833.
- [7] M. Chua, I. Ibrahim, X. Neo, V. Sorokin, L. Shen, S. B. Ooi, Acute aortic dissection in the ed: risk factors and predictors for missed diagnosis, *The American Journal of Emergency Medicine* 30 (8) (2012) 1622–1626. doi:https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ajem.2011.11.017. URL <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0735675711005614>
- [8] A. Asif, P. F. P. Charters, C. A. S. Thompson, H. M. E. I. Komber, B. J. Hudson, J. C. L. Rodrigues, Artificial intelligence can detect left ventricular dilatation on contrast-enhanced thoracic computer tomography relative to cardiac magnetic resonance imaging, *British Journal of Radiology* 95 (1138) (2022) 20210852. arXiv:https://academic.oup.com/bjr/article-pdf/95/1138/20210852/57374057/bjr.20210852.pdf, doi:10.1259/bjr.20210852. URL <https://doi.org/10.1259/bjr.20210852>

- [9] C. Artzner, M. N. Bongers, R. Kärge, S. Faby, G. Heffernan, J. Herrmann, S. L. Nopper, R. M. Perl, S. S. Walter, Assessing the accuracy of an artificial intelligence-based segmentation algorithm for the thoracic aorta in computed tomography applications, *Diagnostics* 12 (8) (2022) 1790.
- [10] S. Mohammadi, M. Mohammadi, V. Dehlaghi, A. Ahmadi, Automatic segmentation, detection, and diagnosis of abdominal aortic aneurysm (aaa) using convolutional neural networks and hough circles algorithm, *Cardiovascular engineering and technology* 10 (2019) 490–499.
- [11] B. S. Kelly, C. Judge, S. M. Bollard, S. M. Clifford, G. M. Healy, A. Aziz, P. Mathur, S. Islam, K. W. Yeom, A. Lawlor, et al., Radiology artificial intelligence: a systematic review and evaluation of methods (raise), *European radiology* 32 (11) (2022) 7998–8007.
- [12] F. Isensee, P. F. Jaeger, S. A. Kohl, J. Petersen, K. H. Maier-Hein, nnu-net: a self-configuring method for deep learning-based biomedical image segmentation, *Nature methods* 18 (2) (2021) 203–211.
- [13] F. Isensee, T. Wald, C. Ulrich, M. Baumgartner, S. Roy, K. Maier-Hein, P. F. Jaeger, nnu-net revisited: A call for rigorous validation in 3d medical image segmentation, in: *International Conference on Medical Image Computing and Computer-Assisted Intervention*, Springer, 2024, pp. 488–498.